

NEW REFORMS IN MODERN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND DIGITAL INTERACTION MODELS WITH CITIZENS

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Abstract. This article analyzes completely new institutional mechanisms for creating a safe environment at the mahalla level, early detection of criminogenic factors and social prevention in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Within the framework of the study, the three-stage vertical management system “mahalla - district – region”, introduced on the basis of the Resolution of the Head of State No. PP-1, the procedure for assigning responsible leaders by name based on a differential approach, and the legal and organizational foundations of the “Social Prevention Week” were studied in depth.

The article systematically analyzes the empirical and demographic data of the “Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY, considers inconsistencies in the criminological categorization of territories, and the problems of forming the mahalla budget. In particular, in the age of digital technologies, the issues of predicting the risk of crimes in the region using artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms and expanding the capabilities of the “E-social prevention” system are scientifically substantiated.

Practical proposals and recommendations aimed at introducing modern digital platforms for digitalization of activities of seven neighborhoods, ensuring data integration and identifying risk groups without the “human factor” using artificial intelligence have been developed. This serves to increase the effectiveness of social prevention.

Key words: *social prevention, neighborhood seven, criminological passport, differential approach, neighborhood budget, digital control, «red» category, institutional responsibility.*

Introduction

Ensuring the rule of law and stabilizing public safety in society is directly determined by the health of the socio-legal environment in the lowest link - the mahalla system. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale institutional reforms to bring the system of early detection and prevention of the criminogenic situation to a completely new level. However, there is a need for a deep scientific analysis of the root causes of family relations, crimes among women and youth, and further improvement of the system of integrated, targeted work on them. Improving the criminogenic situation at the local level requires a scientific assessment of the interrelationship between socio-economic factors (unemployment, poverty, utility infrastructure) and the technical and tactical support of law enforcement agencies. Therefore, the new Presidential Decree No. PP-1 of January 5, 2026 legally strengthened the system of vertical management, differential distribution, and strict personal responsibility in the direction of creating a safe

environment in mahallas.

The purpose of this study is to develop recommendations and organizational proposals on the role and importance of digital platforms aimed at increasing the effectiveness of social prevention by comparing the requirements of new regulatory legal acts with empirical data from a real mahalla (“Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY).

Research methodology

2.1. The research process used a systematic approach, comparative legal analysis, assessment of institutional responsibility, grouping of statistical data, and digital forecasting methods.

2.2. The object of institutional analysis was the Presidential Decree No. PP-1 dated January 5, 2026, the attached Regulation “On the Procedure for Conducting the “Social Prevention Week” in the Mahallas of the Republic”, as well as criminological and demographic indicators of the “Ahmad Yassaviy” Mahalla citizens' assembly for 2025–2026, a typical area with a high population located in Tashkent. This information is compared with empirical data collected through the activities of professors, teachers, employees and students of Tashkent State Law University in a real Mahalla (“Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY), and the development of recommendations and organizational proposals for the introduction of digital platforms aimed at increasing the effectiveness of social prevention.

Analysis and results

In accordance with the new procedure for the institution of vertical management and name-by-name connection, in order to prevent crime in neighborhoods early, a system of name-by-name connection of heads of state agencies (the principle of “differential approach”) was introduced based on the level of complexity of the territories. The demographic and socio-economic analysis of the “Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY The demographic structure of the neighborhood, taken as the object of empirical research, indicates a high workload and the presence of potential risk factors. The total population of the neighborhood is 13,878 people:

Men: 7,867, Women: 6,011. Youth: 1,570, Minors: 1,498. Number of families: 4,598.

The analysis of social sphere objects and drivers shows that there are 28 multi-storey buildings and 1407 house yards in the mahalla. The socially vulnerable population is distributed in the «Daftarlar « system as follows: unemployed: 126 people, in the register of poor families: 36 families, in the “Women's Daftari”: 276 people, in the “Youth Daftari”: 2 people.

Unemployment, poverty level, low legal awareness of the population and conflicts in family and marital relations were identified as the main factors creating the ground for crime. A systematic analysis of the criminological passport of the mahalla and the structure of committed crimes revealed a serious disproportion between the criteria of official statistics and regulatory documents. According to the results of 2025, the mahalla was officially included in the “red” category due to the fact that the number of crimes committed increased by 50 percent compared to the corresponding period in 2024. However, according to the criteria of Resolution No. PP-1, the weight of crimes per thousand population for the “red” category should be higher than the district indicator. In the “Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY, 31 crimes per 13,878 inhabitants occur, which indicates that the coefficient is actually lower than or equal to the district level, that is, the mahalla actually deserves the “yellow” category. Prospects for innovative digitization and electronic surveillance In accordance with Resolution No. PP-1, the sector is tasked with the widespread introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies and electronic surveillance systems. The Ministry of Internal Affairs has set the task of launching the “E-nizoli oila” module within the “My Inspector” mobile application and the “E-social prevention” system. Empirical analysis of data collected by professors, teachers, staff, and students of Tashkent State Law University revealed that the digital infrastructure at the «Ahmad Yassaviy» MFI is not fully formed: there are gaps in the integration of surveillance cameras, intelligent facial recognition systems, and real-time communication between the prevention inspector's tablet.

Discussion

Existing digital systems and their principles of operation. Information system «Digital Mahalla». This system is a digital passport of the Mahalla. It forms a database on households in the Mahalla, the demographic composition of the population, social categories (for example, “Iron Notebook”, “Women's Notebook”, “Youth Notebook”). The “Mahalla Seven” (chairman, assistant khokim, youth leader, women's activist, prevention inspector, etc.) register population problems through this system, distribute social assistance in a targeted manner, and work in integration with state bodies.

Information system “E-prophylaxis”

This system, introduced by the Ministry of Internal Affairs, is directly aimed at preventing crime and digitizing the activities of the prevention inspector. An electronic record of persons who are prone to committing offenses, are under

supervision or have previously been convicted, is maintained in the Mahalla. The system analyzes the data and indicates which homes or areas fall into the “red” (high risk) category. Preventive interviews and measures are planned based on an electronic calendar. Although such lists collect a large amount of data, most of them are only of a statistical (reactive) nature. To move the system to a proactive (predictive) stage, it is proposed to introduce the following algorithms: Create an open data part of the “Digital Mahalla” system. Citizens should be able to see the “security rating” of their Mahalla and give anonymous ratings (stars and comments) to the activities of the Mahalla representatives. This system will increase internal competition and the responsibility of Mahalla representatives.

A single conceptual model is needed to optimize the activities of the “Mahalla Mahalla” and move from a reactive approach to a proactive intellectual forecasting stage in reducing the bureaucratic burden and preventing crime. To do this, it is necessary to introduce a proposal for an intelligent neighborhood ecosystem integration model based on Korean experience, based on artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, where each person is monitored by video cameras and their actions are scored.

Below is the model's working algorithm (on the example of a conflict situation).

Step 1

Input of data into the system Information about a certain family in the neighborhood applying for divorce from the Court and Internal Affairs Bureau database or the Court system is automatically transferred to the “Smart Mahalla” system.

Step 2

Artificial intelligence analysis. AI checks the employment status (unemployment) of the residents of this house and whether there have been previous complaints to the internal affairs body about domestic violence, and transfers the family's risk level to the “Yellow” or “Red” category.

Step 3

Formation of a targeted assignment. The only mobile application of the Mahalla women's activist and Mahalla chairman will automatically load the task: “A conflict situation is observed in the Abdullayevs' house, a conversation is recommended within 48 hours”.

Step 4

A Mahalla seven employee visits the house and enters a report into the system. If the situation is serious and the employee is under severe stress, the application will offer him a short psychological exercise or an online session with a psychologist on the same day.

In the Korean experience, based on the behavior of citizens, their personal rating is formed in a digital system and categorized based on the points they have accumulated. Based on the categories, citizens receive privileges in society. This is formed by the fact that they can be motivated by their activity and discipline in society.

Conclusions and proposals

Resolution No. PP-1 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan created a completely new - targeted, scientifically based and digitized model of ensuring public safety in the country. Based on the scientific and empirical research conducted on the example of the “Ahmad Yassaviy” MFY, the following proposals were put forward to improve the system:

In order to increase the effectiveness of the activities of the “Mahalla Seven”, it is necessary to systematically and targetedly develop their skills, based on real indicators of the socio-economic and psychological situation in the region. At the same time, in order to prevent professional deformation and emotional stress of mahalla representatives, it is necessary to introduce a system of protecting them from psychological stress and supporting their psychological development.

Direct integration of service tablets of prevention inspectors into the PPS and search databases of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Full connection of intelligent cameras in the mahalla entry-exit systems to the “E-social prevention” system.

When classifying regions into “red”, “yellow”, and “green” categories, it is necessary to introduce an automated SI assessment program based not only on the total number of crimes, but also on the population density coefficient (weight per thousand people).

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